
International Requirements for Bank Supervision

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Abstract: The article presents a wealth of experience in strengthening banking supervision and solvency in foreign banks in ensuring the financial stability of commercial banks, but also contains a number of problematic aspects. Applying their positive aspects in the practice of banks in our country can be useful in increasing the financial stability of banks and ensuring their solvency.

In assessing the financial stability and soundness of solvency, not only appropriate supervision or monetary policy, but also other factors are important. In particular, financial stability and stable macroeconomic policy in the country, external and internal political stability, and the competitiveness of economic operators are among them.

Key words: Central Bank, Commercial Banks, International Monetary Fund, World Bank, Moody's International Rating Agency, Monetary Policy, Banking Supervision, Financial Stability, Liquidity, Capital.

Introduction. In foreign countries, the Central Bank and mega-regulators have extensive experience and positive results in ensuring the financial stability of banks and strengthening their solvency. An analysis of the current situation in the banking sector shows that there are a number of systemic problems that hinder the development of the banking sector in line with economic reforms and social needs, such as a high level of state intervention in the banking sector, insufficient quality of management and risk management in banks with state participation, and a low level of financial intermediation in the economy.

Today, a number of works are being carried out in our country to increase the efficiency of the banking system, which are set out in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". In particular, issues such as "ensuring that the growth rate of credit investments in the economy (16-18 percent) is commensurate with the growth rate of the nominal volume of gross domestic product, in particular, attracting foreign bank loans worth \$486.0 million within the framework of 13 investment projects by the end of 2022" were raised[1].

Literature analysis. In the conditions of the current market economy, no state can be imagined without a banking system, since commercial banks belong to the category of financial intermediaries and perform the function of an important mechanism of society in the inter-sectoral and inter-regional redistribution of monetary capital. The process of creating new obligations, as well as the exchange of these obligations for obligations of other counterparties, is the essence of financial intermediation.

Financial and economic analysis of the activities of any economic entity and one of its main tasks is to assess the financial reliability and stability of this entity. It is of great importance that a financially stable bank can quickly recover in the event of any difficult, large losses, and maintain its position in the market.

V.G. Artemenko in his scientific works connects stability with solvency and involves assessing

their financial stability based on absolute and several indicators. The conclusions are that solvency is assessed by the timely fulfillment of payment obligations by economic entities, as well as financial stability is assessed on the basis of cash flow analysis[2]. At the same time, it is clear that there is no connection between the stability of banks and their reliability in this system of indicators.

O.V. Efimova recommends in her research that it is necessary to use a system of other indicators of financial stability. In the opinion of the scientist, this generalized system of indicators should include the return on capital indicator, which comprehensively indicates the growth of banks' capital, and the share of capital in total liabilities as a second indicator, as well as the structure of assets, capital turnover, profitability, fixed and variable costs when assessing financial stability[3].

The International Monetary Fund publishes Financial Soundness Indicators (FSI) of both core and advisory nature. Of the financial soundness indicators, 12 are core indicators, while 26 are advisory indicators.

The core indicators of financial soundness include indicators such as capital adequacy, asset quality, profit and profitability, liquidity, and market risk sensitivity, while advisory indicators cover banks, other financial institutions, corporate companies, households, market liquidity, and the real estate market[4].

The Financial Soundness Indicators have been published by the International Monetary Fund since 2001, and today its ratings are published for countries around the world.

The purpose of financial stability indicators is to reflect the current financial situation through a macroprudential analysis of the financial system of countries, to implement the Financial Sector Assessment Program (FSAP) by the IMF and the World Bank and to publish reports on the stability of the financial system of countries (Financial System Stability Assessment—FSSA), and to assess the stability of the country's financial institutions, counterparties, and households[5].

Research results. The assessment of the financial stability of a commercial bank is closely related to the concept of liquidity of a commercial bank. A bank without liquidity cannot be solvent. In practice, it is precisely illiquidity that is the main reason for the insolvency of banks, leading to their bankruptcy and instability of the banking system.

The methodology for ensuring the financial stability of commercial banks, including international financial organizations, is of great importance.

The methodology for ensuring the financial stability of banks, developed by international rating companies, can be cited by the international rating agency "Moody's".

Table 1. Methodology of determining the financial stability of commercial banks by the international rating agency “Moody’s”[6]

Financial indicators	Categories of banks				
	A	B	C	D	E
The ratio of the amount of profit before provisioning to the amount of the bank's average assets at risk	3.5% and above	2,4%-3,5%	1,4%-2,4%	0,5%-1,4%	0.5% and below
The ratio of net profit to the average total amount of assets at risk	2.0% and above	1,7%-2,0%	1,0%-1,7%	0,3%-1,0%	0.3% and below
(Market funds - liquid assets) / Total assets x 100%	-10%	-10%-0%	0%-10%	10%-20%	20% and above
Tier 1 capital adequacy, in percent	10% and above	8%-10%	6%-8%	4%-6%	4% down
Unused capital as a	7% and	5,5%-7,0%	4,0%-5,5%	2,5%-4,0%	4%

percentage of the average total assets at risk	above				down
(Expenses/Revenues) x 100 %	Below 45 percent	45%-55%	55%-65%	65%-80%	80% and above
(Non-performing loans / Gross loans) x 100 %	Below 0.8 percent	0,8%-2,0%	2,0%-5,0%	5,0%-12,0%	12% and above
Non-performing loans / (Share capital + loan loss provision), in percent	less than 10 percent	10%-20%	20%-30%	30%-50%	50% and above

According to Table 1, Moody's International Rating Agency uses five main indicators to assess the financial stability of commercial banks. These are: profitability, liquidity, capital adequacy, efficiency, and asset quality. This serves to increase the effectiveness of assessing the financial stability of commercial banks.

The main goal of calculating financial stability indicators of commercial banks is to provide users with information about the degree to which a financial institution operates stably. Comparing these indicators at the international level serves to shed more light on the essence of the indicator. For this purpose, indicators for calculating financial stability were first developed and recommended by experts of the International Monetary Fund in 1992. Some changes were made in 2002 and last in 2006. These financial stability indicators total 39, which are divided into 2 groups. The first group includes the main indicators (regarding the banking system) and consists of 12 financial indicators. The second group includes 27 indicators recommended for use in calculating the financial stability of non-bank financial institutions, enterprises and households. Since the activities of commercial banks are the object of research, we found it necessary to study the indicators of the first group. The recommendations presented in Table 2 below are recommendations of the International Monetary Fund, which are currently being implemented by the European Central Bank. The calculation of financial stability indicators of commercial banks and their constant monitoring will help banks effectively manage various negative situations that may arise in the future. We have studied these recommendations in assessing the financial stability of commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Their composition is presented below.

Table 2. Indicators of financial stability of the International Monetary Fund[7].

t/r	Category Indicator	Category Indicator
1.	Capital adequacy Asset quality	Total capital to risk-weighted assets ratio
		Tier 1 capital to risk-weighted assets ratio
		Provisions allocated to problem loans to assets ratio
2.	Rate of income and profitability	Problem loans to total loans ratio
3.	Liquidity	Return on assets ratio (ROA)
		Return on equity ratio (ROE)
		Interest income ratio to gross profit ratio
		Non-interest expenses ratio to gross profit ratio
4.	Capital adequacy	Liquid assets ratio to total assets ratio
		Liquid assets ratio to short-term liabilities ratio
5.	Asset quality	Net open currency position of the bank to capital ratio

Of the above indicators, the capital adequacy ratio shows the degree to which the bank can withstand sudden financial losses, while the asset quality shows the degree to which the bank is able to pay. Income and profitability indicators show the degree to which the bank can cover losses without affecting its capital. The liquidity level shows the degree to which the bank can overcome cash flow problems. Foreign currency risk shows the extent to which changes in the market prices of the bank's assets in foreign currencies affect the bank's activities.

Conclusion. The financial stability of commercial banks, on the one hand, is aimed at expanding and increasing the financial activities of banks, and on the other hand, investing in various sectors and areas for the development of the economy requires close attention to issues such as assessing the liquidity of commercial banks. Determining ways and methods to ensure the financial stability of banks is of particular relevance, and the bank should conduct its activities smoothly and closely align its activities with the goals of achieving long-term positive results.

The main goal of banking supervision is to protect the interests of bank customers and creditors. The adequacy and effectiveness of supervision over the activities of banks is the main factor in ensuring the stability of the banking system and strengthening confidence in banks. In recent years, the increased risk of bank failure has necessitated the continuous improvement of supervision over banking activities. By the 1980s, the banking supervision system began to take shape on an international scale, and at the same time, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision was formed. Considering the high-speed development and integration of the banking system, the requirements of this committee are increasing year by year.

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